

Leveraging Energy Access Explorer to prioritize healthcare facilities electrification in Cameroon

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Executive Summary

This report demonstrates the leverage of Energy Access Explorer, an interactive online platform mapping the state of energy access in underserved areas across Africa and Asia. The platform is leverage to prioritize health care facilities electrification in Cameroon. Results show maps made of one default raster unit of analysis with the area and the population share and another one, summarizing the results of administrative divisions to highlight areas where potential demand for energy services is highest including healthcare facilities. Based on the analysis, the government should start with the Far-North, West and North-West regions which are the priority areas for electrification. From the supply index in population-density share, more than 3 million of people are concerned by the electrification. This work is addressing to the government and energy planners' developers. They now have the visibility to be able to guide electrification policies including health establishments in both urban and rural areas.

Keywords: Energy Access Explorer, priority, webmapping, SDG7, Productive uses, Health, Cameroon

1. Introduction

The health facilities in Cameroon are unevenly distributed from one region to another throughout the national territory. However, those located in rural areas are facing challenges linked to energy access. About 40% of them are located in rural areas. Two out of three Health care facilities has no access to the national electricity grid. The objective of this report aims to prioritize the localities which require energy intervention in order to promote access to several in particular in health facilities. We will use Energy Access Explorer, an interactive online platform mapping the state of energy access in underserved areas. The different indices will cover 4 conceptual indexes of the platform such as Energy access potential, demand index, supply index, and assistance need index. Those will give indicators as the results of the methodology using a collection of energy, socio-economic, and geospatial data.

2. Methodology

Energy Access Explorer needs geospatial data to assess electrification access and intervention. Its model is based on the demand and the supply datasets (Figure 1). Three types of GIS data formats are compatible with the platform: the vector file (line, point, polygon), the raster image file (pixel) and Excel files (CSV format). The process consists in visualizing all of these data in QGIS. This visualization will be used to clean the data by renovating the attributes for example, by reclassifying or deleting certain elements from the attributing table if it is a shapefile. This process permits to apply the right cartographic projection to the vector or raster file. It is good to note that the EAE platform is entirely in degree for the following EPSG WGS84/4326.

Downloading files on the platform through the back-end following the processing procedure. Shapefile files will have to be converted in GeoJSON format before uploading on the platform through the back-end.

Figure 1. Datasets needed for Energy Access Explorer

Source: World Resources Institute (WRI), 2023

The case of prioritization of health facilities uses a set of geospatial data. We look for data coming from the national utility of Energy, Ministry of Public Health, and from the Open-Source Data Sharing platforms. From the first one, we have electricity distribution lines made of transmission and distribution lines, and substations distribution. For the second one, we look for dataset of distribution healthcare facilities throughout the country. These are in vector data format in points in terms of geolocated health facilities. The third one dataset comes from Humanitarian HDX, an Open-Source Data Sharing platforms where the Relative Wealth Index data can be downloaded as a demand (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Useful layers for the prioritization of health facilities case

Source: Energy Access Explorer. EMP-A, Ghana 2024

3. Results

To prioritize health facilities for energy access interventions, we have five types of datasets as layers to be loaded to the platform. User interactions is useful to add filters and some configurations to displays expected results according to the research question. Multi-criteria analysis will help to identify areas where electrification and socio-economic development can be linked. The linkage is important to solve the need unserved populations and area. According to data and criteria, Energy Access Explorer combines data in multi-criteria analysis to give an output result based on the data from both the demand and the supply. The main finding result show an integrated analysis of localities of the highest number of health care facilities with a map (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Main finding of the case study: Raster analysis

Source: Energy Access Explorer Output, 2024

This analysis is based on our own criteria. The platform generates a custom geospatial analysis based on the criteria you entered. The analysis shows four indices around population share and area share. Index score generated by EAE is presented at different scale. We have raster analysis and administrative priority (Figure 4). In the figure below, result map of administrative priority is a summarize by subdivisions. Cameroon has three types of state divisions: Region, Division and Subdivision.

Figure 4. Main finding of the case study: Administrative Priority

Source: Energy Access Explorer output, 2024

In addition to identify keys areas where we can prioritize energy access for Healthcare facilities, EAE displays this summary as charts where we find the area affected by the analysis (figure 5)

Figure 5. Table of areas share and population density per indices

		ENERGY ACCESS EXPLORER				
AREA SHARE		low	low-med	medium	med-high	high
Energy Access Potential		4298	77144	13398	1311	87
Demand Index		28946	62096	4881	252	63
Supply Index		181	3248	16310	48829	27670
Assistance Need Index		91	36468	54110	5375	194

		ENERGY ACCESS EXPLORER				
POPULATION-DENSITY SHARE		low	low-med	medium	med-high	high
Energy Access Potential		148570	3327250	2867677	1034966	864009
Demand Index		945837	4309407	1811313	402372	773543
Supply Index		7337	234832	660169	4173757	3166377
Assistance Need Index		3815	1937320	3904217	2136547	260573

Source: Energy Access Explorer, 2024

In the previous figure, Demand Index in the area share defines that, more than 5,000 areas can be identified to start electrification, including health facilities. For the Supply Index, more than 27,000 sites to start electrification production for the highest-level frame. For the population-density share, about 9 million of people will be impacted in the short or long term.

5. Discussion

The objective of the analysis is to powering healthcare facilities in Cameroun. By displaying the analysis from various geospatial sources according to the demand and the supply side of the platform, the main analysis shows a prioritization aligns on the population density. The high-level planning of energy access in a country can be evaluated with Energy Access Explorer. A potential technology can be prevented in order to help the deployment of minigrid in some localities where access is needed. To do it faster as the SDG time remain about five years to 2030, photovoltaic energy can be leverage to enhance the access. Cameroon has a large Global Horizontal irradiation with relevant Photovoltaic Power Potential. GHI is over 2000 kWh/m² (figure 6).

Figure 6. Level for Global Horizontal Irradiation for Cameroon

(Source: WorldBank, ESMAP, SOLARGIS, 2018)

Localities concern by the healthcare facilities are those developers can expand their business to enhance energy access are the ones situated in the same areas of healthcare facilities. Potential interventions and research can be made in the healthcares located in some localities where the demand index is the highest one. It means where the demand of energy services is high according to the population density. Another intervention found is the supply index indicators. This index shows us sites with high potential for developing electricity generation. The high number supply is about 54 268 areas where we can expand electricity generation within the healthcare facilities.

The distribution of the healthcare facilities across the country is unevenly distributed. Most of them are concentrated in two important regions of the Cameroon, Douala and Yaounde, the capital. Energy Access Explorer shows a distributed map healthcare (figure 7). The Far-North, and North-west regions are the ones concerned over ten region the country has. Potential areas for the implementation of new sites for developing electrification generation ca be done in those regions

Figure 7. Unevenly distributed health cares across the country

Source: Energy Access Explorer, 2024

The financial aspects of the analysis produced by EAE can be supplemented with OnSSET. If EAE does not directly give us some financial information on the amounts in terms of electrification by locality, OnSSET can give us a global amount for the country to achieve electrification on a given date. Using OnSSET allows you to know the financial aspects of the electrification of health facilities; or give the overall figures that we can interpret to prevent interventions in the areas that EAE prioritizes during the analysis.

7. Conclusion

By taking advantage of Energy Access Explorer for the prioritization of health facilities, we deduced that health facilities are present in localities which have a significant population density. Two analytical maps in raster format are produced by EAE. The first concerns a visualization of the scenario of the prioritization of health facilities. The other concerns localities with a high index in which electricity production can be programmed according to the population density and the number of health facilities present. Data are collected and uploaded to the platform is loaded one by one to help create and use the analysis results. Two trends emerge on the Supply index and Demand index respectively for the area share and the population density-share showing significant figures. Indeed, there is a high presenting the greatest number of health facilities. Demand index focuses on demand indicators to identify where demand in energy access is the highest. Supply index indicates sites with high potential electrification generation.

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